

ABSTRACT ISSUES OF INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE IN MUSIC EDUCATION

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Abstract: Performing art is a constantly developing process. Music performance, like other fields, is developing year by year. It is important that the musical education system is carried out organically in the teaching of musical performance. The systematic organization of music education is the main factor for the development of a performer as a skilled musician.

Key words: Instrument performance, musical education, student, musician, student, composer, ensemble.

Introduction:

Consistency in the system of musical education is the main factor for a musician to acquire perfect knowledge and become a mature specialist. This process includes children's music and art schools, secondary specialized music schools and higher education institutions.

The growth of performance culture in Uzbek folk instruments, mastering the works of world classical composers, creation of special works by Uzbek composers for folk instruments are an important basis for the further development of performance art in Uzbek folk instruments. It's done. At the same time, the issue of training highly qualified scientific-pedagogical and executive personnel was also put on the agenda. The development of performance in Uzbek folk instruments in later periods was closely related to the activities of the Tashkent (now Uzbekistan) state conservatory. Since 1948, education in the performance of folk instruments has been started in music higher educational institutions of our country, including the Tashkent (now Uzbekistan) State Conservatory named after M. Ashrafiy. A. Petrosyans was in charge of the department of Uzbek folk instruments, selection of students, preparation of study plans. The services of V. Uspensky, M. Ashrafiy, A. Petrosyans, I. Blagoveshensky, B. Gienko, G. Sobitov in establishing professional education in the performance of Uzbek folk instruments in the land of knowledge are incomparable.

Performing arts is a constantly developing process. At all stages of the musical education system, it is important for the musician to acquire theoretical and practical knowledge at the level of demand, and to be able to correctly form the acquired knowledge and skills for the development of performance skills.

Through this lecture, we will consider the issues of teaching student performance at various stages of the musical education system.

It is known that learning to play a professional musical instrument begins at school age. In order for the young generation to develop as a mature musician in the future, the knowledge and skills they acquire at the music school are important. In fact, in order for the building to be strong and serve for a long time, its foundation must be strong. Music school also serves as a foundation for a musician. The main task of the music school is to direct the young generation to music and other types of art and to form their abilities correctly. Children's respect and attention to our national values and traditions will develop here. Spiritual level, aesthetic taste begins to form. At first sight, he begins to learn communication with others, community relations, stage culture together with art. He develops a love for his instrument. Naturally, the development of performance art has an impact on the teaching method and performance practice in children's music and art schools. Today, the need for new works, i.e. repertoire, for teaching children in music and art schools is increasing. The creation of training manuals and textbooks that meet the requirements of today's education system serves to prevent these needs.

The teaching methodology in children's music and art schools is to provide the student with the first information about the instrument, to set the performance position (postanovka) on the instrument correctly, and to gradually learn theoretical knowledge. starts with learning.

The student's talent, listening ability, memorization ability, sense of rhythm are tested in the music school entrance exams. Naturally, some students may have a lower sense of rhythm, and some may have hearing impairments. It is necessary to correct these shortcomings and develop musical ability. That is, it is advisable to work more on rhythm during the teaching process with a student with a lower ability to feel rhythm. During the lessons, the teacher plays different rhythms by clapping and requires the student to repeat this rhythm, which encourages him to gradually develop his ability to feel the rhythm. Of course, in this process, it is necessary to gradually move from a simple, simple rhythm to a complex one.

In the first lessons, the student is told about the history of the origin of his instrument, the structure of the instrument, famous teachers - musicians who played on this instrument, the importance of the instrument in the educational process, its place in the orchestra. it is appropriate to give general concepts. It is important to correctly form the performance position (pastanovka) on the

instrument. It is necessary to pay special attention to the correct sitting of the student from the first lessons. Even a small mistake in the sitting position has a negative impact on the student's poor performance skills and the development of the body. The main task that is important in this is to place a post, taking into account the length of the student's height, arms and legs, while teaching him to sit properly. That is, it is an important task of the teacher to develop him as a musician based on the individual situation of each student. Music theory and solfeggio are taught in music schools along with playing an instrument. Perfect mastery of these subjects is important for the performer. Failure to thoroughly master the theoretical sciences in music has a negative effect on the performer's future education.

In order to increase the student's musical knowledge, it is appropriate to conduct reading lessons from musical works. Learning to read sheet music helps the student to increase the speed of reading music. Reading sheet music is also necessary in orchestra and ensemble classes. Thoroughly mastering this activity will certainly positively help the student's future learning.

Thus, the knowledge and skills acquired by the student in the children's music and art school in terms of musical performance must meet the following requirements in accordance with the educational system:

- to have complete information about their instruments and their families;
- to be able to distinguish the sound timbre of one's instrument families;
- to be able to perceptively perform samples from the works of technicians and composers of various genres;
- being able to be an accompanist solo and in an ensemble;
- being able to read musical works from sheet music;
- to have an understanding of folk music heritage;
- knowledge of musical terms;
- knowledge of musical means of expression;
- to be able to perform music samples of world nations and works of composers;

Thorough mastery of the above requirements is the foundation for the student to acquire knowledge in the next stages of education.

A student who graduates from a children's music and art school goes to the next stage of education. This stage is secondary specialized educational institutions. The first stages of the student's orientation to the profession begin during the educational process in secondary specialized educational institutions. The issue of developing a student both as a skilled musician and as a pedagogue

lies in secondary special educational institutions. Unlike a children's music and art school, a student learns professional performance skills and independent work at a secondary special educational institution. As mentioned above, each student's ability to learn is not the same. It is important to take into account these aspects in the educational process. Therefore, it is appropriate for the teacher-performer to work taking into account the extent to which the children have mastered the knowledge and skills in the music and art school. Of course, the teacher is very important for the performer to acquire knowledge and skills and become a skilled musician. There are also cases where students who have acquired average knowledge in a music school, but their performance capabilities are not up to the required level, acquire knowledge at an excellent level in secondary special education, develop their performance capabilities as performers, and have high can achieve results. This, of course, goes back to the quality of education in the secondary school and the pedagogical skills of the specialist teacher.

So, let's consider the educational system of the secondary special educational institution as an example of a musical instrument. In most cases, there are some shortcomings in the performance of students who have graduated from a music school and come to continue their education in secondary specialized educational institutions. For example, shortcomings observed in the performance situation (postanovka), underdevelopment of the speed of reading notes, underdevelopment of the skills of working with an accompanist, and insufficient mastery of musical-theoretical sciences. In the first lessons, it is appropriate to check the student's knowledge acquired in the music school, performance possibilities, repertoire of performed works, knowledge about his instrument. After studying the student's performance capabilities, the lessons are organized taking into account these capabilities. At first, it is recommended that the student perform smaller, less complicated works. Gradually, the works become more complicated. When memorizing a piece of music, the student should be taught to work in phrases. This will greatly help memorizing the work easily.

Another important aspect is teaching the student to tune his instrument. The ability to hear plays an important role in this. Listening tuning is very important in orchestra and ensemble classes. Whether it's a concert program or a variety of auditions, before performing a piece on stage, the instrument's tone is checked first. If the student's hearing is good, he can tune his instrument

independently. No matter how skillfully the melody is performed, if the instrument is not tuned, the work will lose its essence.

A performer who wants to become a skilled musician must work on himself a lot. He should play his instrument every day, not only work on a piece of music, but first of all, he should play a lot of exercises and gammas.

Current requirements show that the demand for highly educated specialists in our country is increasing year by year. Based on this point of view, at the moment, young people are trying to get knowledge in higher education institutions.

There are a number of higher education institutions in our country that provide education in the field of culture and art. In particular, the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek National Music Art Institute named after Yunus Rajabi, the National Pop Art Institute named after Botir Zakirov under the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, etc.

In higher education, the performer consolidates the knowledge and skills acquired in primary and secondary special education, performance skills. In higher education, the aspects that are given more importance in the performance of a musical instrument, more attention is paid to the artistry and the essence of the content in the performance of the work. There are some problems in the performance of a musical instrument at the stage of higher education. In particular, there are deficiencies in the repertoire. There is a lack of works to play on the dutor alto. Considering this shortcoming, our Uzbek composers are creating works. Master musicians are adapting the Kazakh folk tunes performed on the dombra for the dutor alto instrument. Dutor and dombra instruments are very similar in structure and performance style. However, the repertoire is still not enough. Composers are invited to write new works for the dutor instrument.

In higher education, the goal of education is for a student to become a professional performer. There are several requirements for skillful performance of the piece. Skillful performance of complex pieces is not just about playing the piece at a fast tempo. Its artistic aspects are also of great importance in the performance of the work. The lack of artistic principles in the performance of the work is often observed among students entering higher education. Before starting to learn to play a piece of music, you need to understand the content of the piece. For this, it is recommended to get acquainted with the composer, the period of writing, the genre, and the form of the work.

In this way, the performer learns the knowledge taught at each stage of musical education at the required level, works on himself regularly, and is properly guided as a performer, which serves to make him a skilled musician in the future.

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